

THE ROLE OF LISTENING IN INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE

Qurbonboyev Shahzod Ikrom o'g'li

Mamatov Sardor G'ayrat o'g'li

3rd year students at Djizzakh branch of The National University of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Abduraxmanova Zilola Yoqubjon qizi

Supervisor:

Assistant teacher in the department Foreign Languages at Djizzakh branch of
The National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

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ANNOTATION

This article gives information about the role of listening in intercultural competence. It has several paragraphs, which gives a full data about article. It is based on What is the role of listening in communication? Why is listening an important skill? What is active listening in intercultural communication? What is intercultural listening? In this article, candidates can learn how to be a good learner and do every task to achieve good results in their study. Also, we mentioned several ways of how to achieve good listening knowledge in the field of intercultural competence easily and effectively.

Key words: Role of listening, active listening, intercultural communication, intercultural listening, intercultural competence.

What is the role of listening in communication?

To listen, we need to make a conscious effort not to just hear what people are saying but to take it in, digest it and understand. Not only does listening enhance your ability to understand better and make you a better communicator, it also makes the experience of speaking to you more enjoyable to other people. The role of listening within an intercultural context should be to actively engage with the verbal stimuli of speakers in order to identify and mediate precise reinforcement of such verbal behavior.

Why is listening an important skill?

It can help you to navigate through difficult conversations. More than that, it helps improve overall communication, builds a better understanding and ultimately leads to better relationships with family, friends and co-workers.

Benefits of Active Listening

- Active Listening Builds Trust and Strong Relationships.
- Active Listening Can Help You to Resolve Conflict.
- Active Listening Prevents You From Missing Important Information.
- Active Listening Enables You To Identify or Anticipate Problems.

- Active Listening Helps You To Build More Knowledge.

What is active listening in intercultural communication?

Most times when we are communicating with someone we are actively forming, in our own minds, what we are going to say next, after the other person stops talking. This takes our attention off the other person and we tend to miss what they are saying. Listening involves more than just hearing, it also involves responding to what someone is saying. This process is called active listening.

Active listening' is a communication skill crucial to doing cross-cultural business. As a skill, it requires the listener to become attuned with the speaker in order to confirm what they have heard and moreover, to confirm the understanding of both parties. However, active engagement may differ across cultures. Active listening can be considered one of the more challenging skills in the field of communication. Despite how simple this concept may appear to be at first, when one looks closer it becomes apparent that there is no universal definition to describe this method, and becoming proficient means hard work in practical terms.

Active listening is about listening with sincerity/ sensitivity and creating a climate of where equality, freedom, permissiveness, understanding, acceptance and warmth (Rogers & Farson 1987). There are various techniques to help create such a positive atmosphere.

The importance of cross-cultural sensitivity becomes important when looking to create such an atmosphere of trust in order to relay the desired response to the sender and to avoid miscommunication. In cross-cultural interactions there are certain discrepancies of how to create such an atmosphere of trust and what is considered as appropriate behavior in active listening, depending on the culture(s) one is dealing with.

What is intercultural listening?

Listening in an intercultural context is the process by which people of different cultures listen to each other to facilitate good communication. Notice above that the process of listening demands that we mindfully listen to what the "other" is saying.

Listening is appreciated across cultures because it signals interest and respect and creates the opportunity for dialogue. This will always be a key skill to develop whether you are communicating with someone from a different culture, in another language, or learning about people's life experiences.

Strategies for active listening include the following:

- Focus your full attention on the other person talking. Face them and maintain eye contact, and be sure you are at the same level. If they are standing – you should stand, if they are sitting – you should sit.
- Ask good questions. Don't accuse or blame in your questioning. Try to look for hidden meaning. Ask open-ended questions and make sure your tone of voice is sincere. For example, "What do you think we should do about the situation? What do you feel are the options?"
- Keep yourself from judging what the other person is saying. Try not to assume that you know what they mean or what they are thinking.

The role of listening in intercultural competence lessons

As a student I assimilated knowledge in the field of intercultural competence at university. During this period many stumbling blocks happened with me to comprehend the real meaning and the importance of this subject. As this subject is mainly related to many cultures we are taught about various cultures. While we are learning we also learnt about the role of listening in this subject. We are showed many videos that represent various cultures. Through these videos I learnt how to be a good listener while having a communication with people from different cultures. Moreover that, I realized that being a good listener can help us to better understand our peers and have a heated conversations. All in all, this subject really helped me to improve my knowledge on foreign cultures and also taught me being a good listener during communications as giving valuable examples of significance of listening in intercultural competence.

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